

READING ENHANCEMENT WORKSHEETS IN ENGLISH FOR GRADE 8 STUDENTS

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Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English for Grade 8 Students

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Abstract

This study attempted to develop and evaluate Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English for Grade 8 Students at San Jose National High School, in the Schools Division of Antipolo during the School Year 2023-2024. This further aimed to enhance the reading comprehension skills of Grade 8 students at San Jose National High School. Descriptive method of research using a researcher-made survey questionnaire as the main research instrument was employed in this paper. Fifteen (15) English teachers and fifteen (15) English Master Teachers were asked to assess the developed reading material. Based on the findings, The English teachers and Master Teachers evaluated the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in terms of all parts as Very Satisfactory showing no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents. The respondents provided comments and suggestions to further enhance the developed learning material.

Keywords: *reading, worksheets, Grade 8 English*

Introduction

Reading competency is a combination of knowledge and skills that allow a person to select, understand, organize information provided in sound and letter form, and successfully use it for public and personal purposes. This definition reflects that reading is considered a kind of cognitive activity and is aimed at extracting information from texts, understanding and interpreting it. In this interpretation, the concept of reading competency is close to information competence.

Reading is an important part of a person's language proficiency. In the academic context, reading is considered one of the most important skills that students need to acquire because the ability to read texts greatly affects students' academic performance, particularly in cases where they must read for their specialist subject (Bastug, 2018).

In modern society, the ability to read cannot be reduced only to mastering the technique of reading, it is a constantly evolving set of knowledge, skills, and abilities, that is, the quality of a person that must be improved throughout his life in various situations of communication activity (Soloveichik, 2018).

According to Spector (2021), at this age, reading fluency is essential for academic advancement in general since problems with this skill may limit students' ability to grasp other topics as they advance through the grades.

However, it is undoubtedly true that one of the enormous challenges that are facing right now by the Department of Education in the time of post-pandemic is the teaching of reading. The public health crisis has intervened with the learner's exposure to reading and literacy resulting in fewer learners who can read independently and comprehend the text, which results in an increased number of non-reader learners.

Likewise, in 2018, at least 78 percent of students in the Philippines failed to reach minimum levels of proficiency in each of the three PISA subjects, with a wide gap by socioeconomic status. Philippines ranked higher in PISA result in 2022 compared to the result in 2018. The country ranked 77th out of 81 countries. It, once again, produced the lowest proficiency in three PISA subjects.

Therefore, teachers and school administrators must address the reading problems and carefully evaluate plans and procedures for the improvement of the reading abilities of the learners. Collaboration is highly needed, especially in these challenging times. They must take action to help learners improve their reading skills to succeed in school and life.

In San Jose National High School, the prevailing effect of the two-year homeschooling is still felt when reading performance of the students is considered. Based on the results of the post-assessment test as regards the reading level of the Grade 8 students, there were still ninety-two (92) learners who were identified to be under the frustration level of reading. This means that they were not able to comprehend the texts that were given to them because of poor reading comprehension skills.

In addition, as the English teacher of Grade 8, the researcher observes that the students are reluctant to read or do not read at all because they do not know the correct pronunciation of the word.

With connection to the above context, development of enhancement materials to mend the reading gaps of the students is considered deemed necessary. Cayabyab (2019) believed that in order to improve learning experiences of the students, they must be exposed to different learning materials which are properly evaluated and validated. In addition, she reminded the materials developer to be mindful to include only the appropriate and relevant topics in their materials.

The researcher, being a language and reading teacher, targeted to develop worksheets that would serve as enhancement materials to help the Grade 8 students improve their reading skills. Moreso, the researcher believed that the developed learning materials would be

of great help to the English 8 teachers as they could utilize these in conducting reading remediation activities.

Research Questions

This study attempted to develop and evaluate Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English for Grade 8 Students at San Jose National High School, in the Schools Division of Antipolo during the School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, it answered the following research questions:

1. What were the top ten (10) most difficult learning competencies in English 8 as perceived by selected English teachers?
2. How did the English teachers and Master Teachers evaluate the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets based on the following parts?
 - 2.1. Learning Goals
 - 2.2. Vocabulary Enhancement Exercise
 - 2.3. Reading Selection
 - 2.4. Learning Activities/Tasks
 - 2.5. Learning Assessment
 - 2.6. Enrichment Exercises
3. Was there any significant difference between the evaluation of the two groups of respondents relative to the parts of the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets?

Literature Review

According to Suhermanto (2019), reading is one of the skills in English which enables people get an information from what they read. Combining information from a text and their own background knowledge to build meaning is a fluent process that readers do.

To Setiawan (2019), reading is the process of looking at a series of written symbols and getting meaning from them. In reading, one uses his/her eyes to receive written symbols like letters, punctuation marks and spaces while the brain converts them into words, sentences and paragraphs that communicate something.

Haymon and Wilson (2020) articulated that reading comprehension is a complex process that requires different building-block skills. One model of reading comprehension purposes that understanding a text requires three levels of skills: literal comprehension, inferential comprehension, and evaluative comprehension.

Meanwhile, "The Importance of Instructional Materials" by Marbas (2018) elucidates the significance of all kinds of learning materials. According to this, materials intended for student use should be appropriate for the subject area and for the age, social development, ability levels, special needs, and learning styles of the students. Mariano, et al. (2019), mentioned that the learner needs to be exposed to a large amount of comprehensible input in their new language to acquire the language. This means that teachers should ensure that reading takes place not only within the classroom but also outside the four corners of the room. This is possible through supplementary activities.

Worktexts are activities that are additional but more useful activities in the English language (Marcelo and Santillan, 2020). This is any non-required instructional material included in a course. Although not required, supplemental activities play a vital role in ensuring that reading continues outside of school and contributes to the mastery of a particular skill.

Another study was done by Hontiveros (2018) entitled Reading Remediation Learning Materials for Grade VII Students. The salient findings showed that the topics included in the developed reading remediation learning materials addressed the least mastered skills based on the results of diagnostic test.

Moreover, Gimena (2023) conducted a study title E-Reading Intervention Packets for Grade 8 Students which aimed to develop and evaluate electronic reading intervention materials for Grade 8. The respondents remarked that the developed E-Reading Intervention Packets are appealing to the students since its feature is adapted from the famous online game Mobile Legends. It is vital because everything today is becoming increasingly digital, and it will be of great help to make learning fun and exciting.

Methodology

Research Design

This study which attempted to describe the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8 employed descriptive method of research utilizing researcher-made survey questionnaire. According to McCombes (2020), descriptive research is used to describe an existing phenomenon, condition, and population as scientifically as possible. Further, the descriptive method entails gathering, evaluating, and presenting the data (Thakur, 2020) which is deemed apposite to the study for it aims to develop Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English for Grade 8 students.

Respondents

The data in this study were gathered from the 15 English teachers and 15 English Master Teachers from the selected schools in Schools

Division of Antipolo City. The researcher used the purposive sampling technique in choosing the respondents. She chose them from the schools in the SDO Antipolo City because she knows them as they belong to one SDO and she once worked with them during the seminars and trainings as regards English subject.

Instrument

This study used two sets of research instruments necessary to gather the needed data. The first set was the survey checklist which served as the basis in identifying the top 10 most difficult learning competencies in Grade 8 as perceived by the selected English teachers.

The second research instrument was the researcher-made survey questionnaire which was used for the evaluation of the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English for Grade 8 students. It had two major parts. Part I contained the criteria for evaluating the developed reading enhancement material in terms of its parts such as Learning Goals, Vocabulary Enhancement Exercise, Reading Selection, Learning Tasks, Learning Assessment, and Enrichment Exercise. The second part was intended to gather the comments and suggestions of the teacher-respondents for further improvement of the learning material.

Procedure

The study had undertaken during the school year 2023-2024. Permission to conduct the study was secured from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Schools Division of Antipolo. After the approval of her letter or request, she then proceeded to the different schools and talked with the School Principals to administer the survey questionnaire.

Fifteen (15) English teachers and fifteen (15) English Master Teachers were asked to evaluate the developed learning materials using the survey questionnaire. The data gathered were carefully interpreted and analyzed using the appropriate statistical tools. Comments and suggestions were also sought for further improvement of the developed material. Maintaining confidentiality, giving counselling, cross-examining the respondents and providing details for this study was taken into consideration.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Top Ten Most Difficult Learning Competencies in English 8 as perceived by English Teachers

Table 1. *Top Ten Most Difficult Learning Competencies in English 8 that can be Used into the Development of Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8 as perceived by selected English Teachers*

<i>Least Mastered Vocabulary Skills</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Explain visual-verbal relationships illustrated in tables, graphs, and information maps found in expository texts	2.88	1
Note implicit signals used by the writers to indicate coherence	4.38	2.5
Deliver a manuscript/memorized oral speech with ease and fluency before an audience	4.38	2.5
Scan for logical connectors to determine the text type	4.50	4.5
Deliver a self-composed speech using all the needed speech conventions	4.50	4.5
Examine biases (for or against) made by the author	5.13	6
Use effective nonverbal communication strategies: gestures and body movements and eye contact, etc.	5.50	7
Judge the relevance and worth of ideas presented in the material viewed	6.00	8
Employ different listening strategies suited to the topic, purpose, and level of difficulty of the listening text	6.13	9
Determine the issue and stand presented in the material viewed	6.71	10

As shown on the table, the top ten (10) most difficult learning competencies (RM no. 306 s 2020) in English 8 as perceived by selected English teachers according to average and rank are the following: Rank 1: Explain visual-verbal relationships illustrated in tables, graphs, and information maps found in expository texts with the average of 2.88; Rank 2.5: Note implicit signals used by the writers to indicate coherence, and Deliver a manuscript/memorized oral speech with ease and fluency before an audience both with the average of 4.38; Rank 4.5: Scan for logical connectors to determine the text type, and Deliver a self-composed speech using all the needed speech conventions both with the average of 4.50; Rank 6: Examine biases (for or against) made by the author with the average of 5.13; Rank 7: Use effective nonverbal communication strategies: gestures and body movements and eye contact, etc. with the average of 5.50; Rank 8: Judge the relevance and worth of ideas presented in the material viewed with the average of 6.00; Rank 9: Employ different listening strategies suited to the topic, purpose, and level of difficulty of the listening text with the average of 6.13, and Rank 10: Determine the issue and stand presented in the material viewed with the average of 6.71.

Evaluation of the Expert-Respondents and the Teacher-Respondents on the Developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners

The English Teachers and Master Teachers evaluated the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8 in terms of learning goals as Very Satisfactory with the obtained Average mean of 3.93 and 3.71 respectively. Based on the result, the two groups of respondents concurred to the idea that the developed learning material has objectives that are easy to understand by the target users and

aligned to expected reading competencies.

Table 2. Evaluation on the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in terms of Learning Goals

A. Learning Goals The learning goals...	Respondents			
	English Teachers		Master Teachers	
	M	VI	M	VI
1. are well-presented and clearly stated.	3.93	VS	3.73	VS
2. are congruent to the topics, learning tasks, and learning assessment.	3.93	VS	3.73	VS
3. provide significant goals relevant to expected skills and knowledge.	3.93	VS	3.60	VS
4. address the needs of the target students.	3.93	VS	3.73	VS
5. lead the learners to the mastery of competencies in reading comprehension.	3.93	VS	3.71	VS
Average Mean	3.93	VS	3.73	VS
3.82- Very Satisfactory				

The result implies that the learning goals included in the material are well- presented and clearly stated, are congruent to the topics, learning tasks, and learning assessment, provide significant goals relevant to the expected skills and knowledge, address the needs of the target students, lead the learners to the mastery of competencies in reading comprehension.

This conforms the study of Domingo (2023) in which the teachers and experts evaluated the learning objectives as one of the parts of the developed learning materials. He mentioned that it is important that the teachers who develop learning materials should make sure that the objectives are parallel to the expected competencies and presented activities.

Table 3. Evaluation on the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in terms of Vocabulary Enhancement Exercises

B. Vocabulary Enhancement Exercises The vocabulary enhancement exercises...	Respondents			
	English Teachers		Master Teachers	
	M	VI	M	VI
1. contain enriching activities targeting the vocabulary skills of the students.	3.87	VS	3.73	VS
2. are included in every topic before each reading material.	3.87	VS	3.67	VS
3. engage learners in interactive learning experiences toward vocabulary development.	3.93	VS	3.60	VS
4. help the students to unlock their difficulties.	3.93	VS	3.80	VS
5. create word association between the unfamiliar terms in the reading text	3.87	VS	3.67	VS
Average Mean	3.89	VS	3.69	VS
3.79- Very Satisfactory				

The English Teachers and Master Teachers evaluated the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8 in terms of vocabulary enhancement exercise as Very Satisfactory with the obtained mean of 3.89 and 3.69 respectively. Based on the result, the two groups of respondents believed that the developed learning material provides engaging and interactive tasks that support the development of the vocabulary skills of Grade 8. The result implies that the vocabulary Enhancement Exercises contain enriching activities targeting the vocabulary skills of the students, are included in every topic before each reading material, engage learners in interactive learning experiences toward vocabulary development, help the students to unlock their difficulties, create word association between the unfamiliar terms and the reading text. unfamiliar words presented in the reading text in the material.

This supports the study of Latina (2019) which cited that preliminary activities in the developed learning materials like vocabulary enhancement are important as this measure prior knowledge of the target audience. Also, she posited that this introductory task of the materials should build students’ schema which they need in the reading of the selection.

Table 4. Evaluation on the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in terms of Reading Selection

C. Reading Selection The reading selection...	Respondents			
	English Teachers		Master Teachers	
	M	VI	M	VI
1. is presented in every lesson.	3.93	VS	3.93	VS
2. is relevant to the target competency.	3.93	VS	3.73	VS
3. contains text that is appropriate for the level of the target students.	3.80	VS	3.73	VS
4. is appropriate and readable.	3.93	VS	3.93	VS
5. contains noteworthy contexts that present the importance of the topic to one’s life.	3.87	VS	3.80	VS
Average Mean	3.89	VS	3.83	VS
3.86- Very Satisfactory				

The English Teachers and Master Teachers evaluated the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8 in terms of reading selection as Very Satisfactory with the obtained mean of 3.89 and 3.83 respectively. Based on the result, the two groups of respondents agreed that the developed learning material presented relevant, appropriate, and accurate reading texts that are connected to the target topic. The result implies that the reading selection is presented in every lesson, is relevant to the target competency, contains text that

is appropriate for the level of the target students, is appropriate and readable, contains noteworthy contexts that present the importance of the topic to one's life. This is parallel to the study of Dikitanan (2020) in which the teachers and expert-respondents evaluated her developed learning material in literature as Very Satisfactory in terms of the reading texts.

Table 5. *Evaluation on the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in terms of Learning Activities*

<i>D. Learning Activities</i> <i>The learning activities...</i>	<i>Respondents</i>			
	<i>English Teachers</i>		<i>Master Teachers</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. provide clear and precise directions/instructions for the target learners.	3.80	VS	3.80	VS
2. contain interesting tasks that catch the students' interest and attention.	3.73	VS	3.80	VS
3. elicit the understanding of the students about the lesson.	3.67	VS	3.73	VS
4. allow learners to use critical thinking skills through engaging activities.	3.87	VS	3.67	VS
5. develop the students' comprehension of the reading selection.	3.80	VS	3.80	VS
Average Mean	3.77	VS	3.76	VS
	3.77- Very Satisfactory			

The English Teachers and Master Teachers evaluated the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8 in terms of learning activities/tasks as Very Satisfactory with the obtained mean of 3.77 and 3.76 respectively. Based on the result, the two groups of respondents approved that the developed learning material contains learning activities that can deepen the learner's knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values through application of what they have learned in the previous part of the material. The result implies that the learning activities provide clear and precise directions/instructions for the target learners, contain interesting tasks that catch the students' interest and attention, elicit the understanding of the students about the lesson, allow learners to use critical thinking skills through engaging activities, develop the students' comprehension of the reading selection.

This is connected to the study of De Ungria (2023) as her developed strategic intervention materials evaluated as Very Much Satisfactory in terms of the engagement part which presented the learning tasks. She cited that it promoted and stimulated higher order thinking skills and contains relevant real- world learning experiences.

Table 6. *Evaluation on the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in terms of Learning Activities*

<i>E. Learning Assessment</i> <i>The learning assessment...</i>	<i>Respondents</i>			
	<i>English Teachers</i>		<i>Master Teachers</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. evaluates students' understanding of the presented lesson.	3.87	VS	3.93	VS
2. provides concrete tasks that allow learners to apply the concept that they learned.	3.67	VS	3.73	VS
3. contains authentic learning experiences that assess students' reading comprehension	3.73	VS	3.87	VS
4. is consistent to the content of the reading selection and other learning tasks.	3.80	VS	3.80	VS
5. is congruent to the learning goal.	3.93	VS	3.93	VS
Average Mean	3.80	VS	3.85	VS
	3.83- Very Satisfactory			

The English teachers and Master Teachers of learning assessment as Very Satisfactory with the obtained mean of 3.80 and 3.85 respectively. Based on the result, the two groups of respondents agreed that the developed learning material measures the acquired knowledge and skills of the students various learning activities that developed their creativity, critical thinking, and other higher level of cognitive skills.

The result implies that the learning assessment of the developed learning material evaluates students' understanding of the presented lesson, provides concrete tasks that allow learners to apply the concept that they learned, contains authentic learning experiences that assess students' reading comprehension, is consistent to the content of the reading selection and other learning tasks, is congruent to the learning goal.

Table 7. *Evaluation on the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in terms of Enrichment Exercises*

<i>F. Enrichment Exercises</i> <i>The enrichment exercises...</i>	<i>Respondents</i>			
	<i>English Teachers</i>		<i>Master Teachers</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. provide activities that deepen the understanding of the students.	3.93	VS	3.93	VS
2. are given to aid the students' knowledge, skills, and attitude.	3.80	VS	3.87	VS
3. engage the learners in tasks that improve their learning of the target reading competency.	3.93	VS	3.93	VS
4. help learners to explore more to enhance their reading comprehension skill.	3.87	VS	3.93	VS
5. are connected to all other parts of the material.	3.73	VS	3.73	VS
Average Mean	3.85	VS	3.88	VS
	3.873- Very Satisfactory			

The English Teachers and Master Teachers evaluated the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8 in terms of enrichment exercises as Very Satisfactory with the obtained mean of 3.85 and 3.88 respectively. Based on the result, the two groups of respondents supported the idea that the developed learning material provided help to enhance skills and understanding of the lesson. The result implies that the Enrichment Exercises provide activities that deepen the understanding of the students, are given to aid the students' knowledge, skills, and attitude, engage the learners in tasks that improve their learning of the target reading competency, help learners to explore more to

This can be associated to the study of Calatrava (2022) in which the researcher's developed learning material was evaluated as Very Satisfactory in terms of its assessment part. He posited that the students were able to produce products based on the concepts they have learned as assessment of their understanding.

Test of Significant difference between the Evaluation of English 8 Teachers and English Master Teachers on the Developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8

Table 8. *Test of Significant Difference between the Evaluation of the Developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8 In terms of Learning Goals*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>t-test</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
English Teachers	3.93	0.12	Failed to reject H_0	Not Significant
Master Teachers	3.71			

It is seen in the table that the computed t Test of 0.12 is greater than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is confirmed. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the evaluation of two groups of respondents on the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in terms of learning goal. Both English Teachers and master Teachers have the same judgement on the developed reading enhancement worksheet in English 8 in terms of learning goals.

Table 9. *Test of Significant Difference between the Evaluation of the Developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8 In terms of Enhancement Exercises*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>t-test</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
English Teachers	3.89	0.23	Failed to reject H_0	Not Significant
Master Teachers	3.69			

It is seen in table that the computed t Test of 0.12 is greater than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is confirmed. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the evaluation of two groups of respondents on the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in terms of Vocabulary Enhancement Exercises. Both English teachers and master teachers have the same judgement on the developed reading enhancement worksheet in English 8 in terms of Vocabulary Enhancement Exercises.

Table 10. *Test of Significant Difference between the Evaluation of the Developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8 In terms of Reading Selection*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>t-test</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
English Teachers	3.89	0.56	Failed to reject H_0	Not Significant
Master Teachers	3.83			

It is seen in the table that the computed t Test of 0.12 is greater than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is confirmed. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the evaluation of two groups of respondents on the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in terms of Reading Selection. Both English teachers and master teachers have the same judgement on the developed reading enhancement worksheet in English 8 in terms of Reading Selection.

Table 11. *Test of Significant Difference between the Evaluation of the Developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8 In terms of Learning Activities*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>t-test</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
English Teachers	3.77	0.93	Failed to reject H_0	Not Significant
Master Teachers	3.76			

It is seen in the table that the computed t Test of 0.12 is greater than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is confirmed. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the evaluation of two groups of respondents on the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in terms of Learning Activities.

Both English teachers and master teachers have the same judgement on the developed reading enhancement worksheet in English 8 in terms of learning Activities.

Table 12. *Test of Significant Difference between the Evaluation of the Developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8 In terms of Learning Assessment*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>t-test</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
English Teachers	3.80	0.66	Failed to reject H_0	Not Significant
Master Teachers	3.85			

It is seen in the table that the computed t Test of 0.12 is greater than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is confirmed. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the evaluation of two groups of respondents on the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in terms of Learning Assessment. Both English teachers and master teachers have the same judgement on the developed reading enhancement worksheet in English 8 in terms of learning Assessment.

Table 13. *Test of Significant Difference between the Evaluation of the Developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8 In terms of Enrichment Exercise*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>t-test</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
English Teachers	3.85	0.82	Failed to reject H_0	Not Significant
Master Teachers	3.88			

It is seen table that the computed t Test of 0.12 is greater than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is confirmed. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the evaluation of two groups of respondents on the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in terms of Enrichment Exercises. Both English teachers and master teachers have the same judgement on the developed reading enhancement worksheet in English 8 in terms of Enrichment Exercises.

Comments and Suggestions given by the Respondents to further improve the Developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8

The following were the comments and suggestions that were given by the teacher-respondents to further improve the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8

Comments

The material contains lessons that are very comprehensive which may allow the learners to understand the lesson.

The reading material is convenient to use and provides interactive activities.

The material provides a variety of learning activities that target different kinds of learners with different learning styles.

The presentation of ideas and contents are well-organized.

The material can significantly increase the achievement of the learners and may provide them opportunities to practice new skills.

All the activities included in the material are inclined with the target most essential learning competencies.

Suggestions

Kindly check thoroughly the material to avoid typographical errors and observe consistency with the format like font style, size, and the likes.

May elicit further the prior knowledge of the students through schematizing in the pre-reading activities.

In the vocabulary enhancement exercises, students may also be asked to get the meaning of words through context clues or create word association between the unfamiliar words and the reading text.

May use localized concepts in the activities.

May utilize integrative activities as well.

May improve other details like color of the images and other aspects of the layout.

May enhance the presentation of the material considering its appeal to the learners so that it can catch more of their attention and interest.

May consider the icons and captions.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

Based on the prescribed Most Essential Learning Competencies for English 8 in all quarters, there were 10 identified topics which were

considered as most difficult and could be used in the development of enhancement materials to improve the reading skills of the students.

Evaluation for the developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8 was found acceptable as Learning Materials to enhance the reading skills of the students. The two groups of respondents share similar views on the Reading Enhancement Worksheets.

The developed Reading Enhancement Worksheets in English 8 can be utilized as effective learning materials in teaching lessons in Research for English 8 learners.

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